

OpenMod Africa

Training Platform

Deliverable No. 1.3

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List of acronyms

GA	Grant Agreement
OM4A	Open Energy System Modelling Toolbox for Africa
OpenMod4Africa	Open Modelling Toolbox for development of long-term pathways for the energy system in Africa, the project that developed the OM4A
PN	Permanent Network
WP	Work Package

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List of Links

OM4A Permanent Network	https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/
OM4A Forum	https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/forum
OM4A Website	https://openmod4africa.eu/
Training Platform	https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@AfricanEnergyModellingNetwork
Toolbox	https://africaenergymodels.net/

Executive Summary

The Horizon Europe Energy project, Open Modelling Toolbox for the Development of Long-term Pathways for the Energy System in Africa (OpenMod4Africa), is a three-year initiative (2023-2026) aimed at equipping African energy stakeholders with an open-access Toolbox for energy analysis, planning, and evaluation tailored to the continent. The latest version of the Toolbox was published in June 2025 and is now accessible at <https://africaenergymodels.net/>. A complementary component of the project, led by WP1 – Capacity Building, is the release of the OpenMod4Africa online Training Platform designed to build local capacity by offering accessible, high-quality training resources to support the use of the ToolBox.

The Training Platform is publicly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/OM4A-Training-Material>, and is complemented by a dedicated YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@AfricanEnergyModellingNetwork>), which hosts a growing collection of tutorial videos and explanatory content. All materials are openly accessible under a Creative Commons license and are provided in both English and French, to ensure inclusivity and broader reach across African regions.

The Training Platform supports self-paced learning and includes structured modules on installing the ToolBox, the fundamentals of energy system modelling by running the models, advanced uses as well as case studies. Further contents will be developed together with the advancement of the OpenMod4Africa project. Those contents will be created in function of the needs raised by the OpenMod4Africa [African Energy Modelling Network](#) (Deliverable 1.5 in the project), which will be also in charge of the maintenance of the platform.

The Permanent Network also features a structured Forum (at <https://africanenergymodellingnetwork.net/forum>) with a Q&A service, where users of the OpenMod4Africa Toolbox can post questions and access answers in a searchable, user-friendly format. This interactive support system aims to foster collective learning and provide ongoing technical assistance to the growing community of African energy modellers.

Overall, the platform plays a central role in achieving the project's capacity-building objectives, ensuring that energy stakeholders are equipped with the knowledge and tools needed for effective, evidence-based energy planning for the African Continent.

This accompanying report provides an overview of the training platform's structure, content, and functionality, and guides users on how to navigate and benefit from the available resources.

1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe Energy project 101118123 - Open Modelling Toolbox for the Development of Long-term Pathways for the Energy System in Africa (OpenMod4Africa) is a three-year initiative (2023-2026) about the development of an energy modelling toolbox for analyses of the future energy and power systems in Africa. The OpenMod4Africa project aims to support long-term energy planning in Africa through the development and dissemination of open-access modelling tools and tailored capacity-building initiatives. Within this framework, the Working Package 1 (WP1) – Capacity building - focuses on empowering African stakeholders by enhancing technical skills, facilitating knowledge transfer, and fostering a robust community of practice around energy system modelling.

A core output of WP1 is the development of the **OpenMod4Africa Training Platform**—a digital space dedicated to training and capacity development both within the Project Partners and the external public. Designed to complement the OpenMod4Africa Toolbox, the platform provides structured, high-quality learning resources in both English and French, thereby ensuring accessibility across linguistic and regional divides.

Overall, the other transversal Tasks of WP1 are the following:

1. Increase competence about the OM4A Toolbox among African scientific experts by organizing workshops, training camps and disseminating training material.
2. Develop training material.
3. Involve African scientific partners from the beginning in OpenMod4Africa in the training activities.
4. Identify further training needs beyond OpenMod4Africa.
5. Develop a permanent network of African energy modellers.
6. Write joint scientific papers.

The outcomes of all these activities also support fulfilling Task 2, i.e., the development of the **OpenMod4Africa Training Material**.

The following chapters describe the platform established for hosting the training material (on GitHub), as well as multiple complementary supports such as a dedicated YouTube channel and a structured Online Forum hosted by the OpenMod4Africa Permanent Network (Deliverable 1.5 in the project).

2. The OM4A Training platform

The OpenMod4Africa online Training Platform is designed to build local capacity by offering accessible, high-quality training resources to support the use of the ToolBox. The Training Platform is publicly available on [GitHub](#) and is complemented by a dedicated [YouTube channel](#). This format supports different learning preferences and ensures that technical content is accessible even to those with limited coding experience. The Permanent Network also features a structured [Forum](#) with a Q&A service, where users of the OpenMod4Africa Toolbox can post questions and access answers in a searchable, user-friendly format. This interactive support system aims to foster collective learning and provide ongoing technical assistance to the growing community of African energy modellers.

2.1 GitHub Repository – Core Training Materials

The main repository of the Training Platform is hosted on [GitHub](#). It provides access to:

- Overall introduction to the OpenMod4Africa Project (including links to relevant websites and social media accounts) and to the ToolBox.
- Step-by-step **installation guides** for each model in the Toolbox.
- Detailed **tutorials** on using and modifying the models.
- Thematic **training modules** covering foundational and advanced topics in energy system modelling.
- Supporting documentation and metadata.

The GitHub structure is organized by model and topic, with folders dedicated to each model: GENeSYS-MOD, plan4res, EV-PV simulator, openTEPES, OnSSET, and InfraFair, as can be seen in Figure 2. Each folder includes a README file (.md files, written in markdown code allowing online visualisation) to guide users through the content and facilitate independent, self-paced learning. README files are provided in both English and French.

Figure 1. OM4A Training Platform main menu

The French version of each training material README file is available in two ways:

1. Within each pinned repository on GitHub, the French README file is included alongside the English version.
2. Via the dedicated repository called French-version, which contains the main project README in French and all translated README files for the training materials.

Figure 2. The models in the training platforms (pinned repository)

In addition, there is a dedicated repository for Questions & Answers, as shown in Figure 3. The Q&A section is organized by model and provides answers to the most frequently asked questions regarding installation, execution, and interpretation of results for each module.

Figure 3 Questions & Answers repository

The GitHub structure has been developed with the support of OpenMod4Africa modelling partners: TU Berlin, Comillas, EDF and EPFL.

2.2 YouTube Channel – Visual Learning Content

While the Training Platform hosted on GitHub primarily offers text-based support, it is complemented by visual resources available through a dedicated YouTube channel, which is linked directly from the GitHub repository.

The [OpenMod4Africa YouTube channel](#) provides a growing collection of video tutorials.

These videos are designed to complement the GitHub material by offering:

- **Explanatory videos** introducing key modelling concepts and model scope.
- **Visual demonstrations of:**
 - Installation of the model;
 - Basic and advanced model run.

The YouTube Channel's Playlists are organized by topic and model, as can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Playlists of the YouTube Channel

The videos have been recorded by the OpenMod4Africa modelling Partners in English; nevertheless, YouTube features allow auto-generating French (as well as other languages) subtitles through the procedure illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1. Steps to insert French, or another preferred language, subtitles in YouTube videos

<p>Step 1</p>	<p>Open the video that you want to watch.</p>	
<p>Step 2</p>	<p>Click on the subtitles button, which is the one underlined in red in this figure.</p>	

<p>Step 3</p>	<p>At this point, click on settings as shown and click on Subtitles/CC (1).</p>	
<p>Step 4</p>	<p>Finally, click on Auto-translate and choose the French language or the language that you prefer.</p>	

The YouTube Channel and its content have been developed with the support of OpenMod4Africa modelling partners: TU Berlin, Comillas, EDF and EPFL.

2.3 Online Forum – Interactive Support and Community Learning

To encourage peer-to-peer support and long-term knowledge exchange, the Training Platform is supported by the [African Energy Modelling Network Forum](#), a space for users to share experiences, tips, and insights.

The Forum includes:

- **Discussion threads** grouped by model, theme, and language (Figure 5).
- A **Q&A section** where users can post technical questions about the Toolbox (Figure 6).
- **Searchable archives** of previously resolved issues.

Forum

Forum

Energy System Modelling: GENeSYS-MOD		Last post
 Input data queries A forum for any discussions regarding input data and assumptions when using GENeSYS-MOD for energy system analysis. 0 Topics - 0 Posts		No topics yet!
 Initial Model Setup Forum for discussions on installing and setting up GENeSYS-MOD, any associated errors or model updates. 0 Topics - 0 Posts		No topics yet!
 Model Results Discussions on understanding, refining and processing model results when using GENeSYS-MOD for energy system analysis. 0 Topics - 0 Posts		No topics yet!
 General For general discussions on developing energy system models, scenarios, research questions, and other topics. 0 Topics - 0 Posts		No topics yet!

Figure 5 Forum structure

General Queries		Last post
Welcome to the Forum – Re ... 1 month ago · Daniel Albert		
 Open data sets – sources and collaboration 0 Topics · 0 Posts		No topics yet!
 Capacity Building & Resources For any questions, resources and discussions related to trainings and capacity building activities. 0 Topics · 0 Posts		No topics yet!

Figure 6. Q&A section of the Forum

The Forum has been developed with the support of SINTEF.

3. Next steps

The continued development and maintenance of the Training Platform will be overseen by the OpenMod4Africa Permanent Network, which will ensure its long-term relevance, responsiveness to user needs, and integration with future developments of the OM4A Toolbox.

Looking ahead, the following next steps are envisaged:

- **Responsive Content Expansion:** New training materials will be developed in response to evolving training needs, as identified by members of the African Energy Modelling Network. This will ensure that the platform remains aligned with real-world challenges and user demands.
- **Focus on Model Integration and Visualisation:** Upcoming training modules will address the interconnections between the different models within the Toolbox and provide guidance on how to use the integrated visualisation tools currently under development. This will support more holistic energy system analysis and scenario building.
- **Ongoing Bilingual Support:** The platform will continue to offer all training materials in both English and French, expanding accessibility and supporting inclusive participation across Africa's diverse linguistic communities.
- **Enhanced Community Engagement:** Further efforts will be made to stimulate user interaction on the Q&A Forum and YouTube channel, encouraging knowledge exchange, peer support, and feedback loops to improve the quality and usability of materials.
- **Sustainability and Governance:** In parallel, strategies will be explored to secure long-term maintenance of the platform – aligning with the governance structure of the Permanent Network.

These actions aim to consolidate the Training Platform as a central, dynamic resource for capacity-building in African energy system modelling, ensuring it evolves alongside the tools, users, and challenges it is designed to support.